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Financial Analysis of Waste-to-Energy (WtE): A FINPLAN Approach

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Executive Summary

This study evaluates the financial viability of a 50 MW Waste-to-Energy (WtE) project in Malaysia using FINPLAN. Findings indicate that blended financing, combining domestic green schemes with affordable loans, is essential for project bankability, while Malaysia's Green Technology Financing Scheme (GTFS) alone is insufficient. WtE projects are highly sensitive to tipping fees, feedstock availability, and transport costs. Sensitivity analysis highlights that a tipping fee range from 74.9 to 82.5 MYR/t ensures a debt service coverage ratio above 1.3 and breakeven ratio below 1, demonstrating financial feasibility. The feedstock threshold was found to be 2,000 t/day and 1,700 t/day without and with carbon credit, respectively. This highlights the role of carbon credit may play in addressing issues around feedstock dependency. Lastly, the transport cost analysis indicates that a collection radius of less than 5 km is required to maintain financial feasibility. Based on these findings, it is recommended to establish structured and consistent tipping fee framework to ensure stable revenue. Furthermore, the incorporation of carbon credit can further strengthen the project resilience on fluctuating feedstock. To ensure a consistent and reliable feedstock supply, strategic location planning is essential. To conclude, this analysis serves as a practical tool to support the long-term viability of WtE projects while aligning their development with Malaysia's circular economy and climate targets.

1. Introduction

Malaysia holds significant renewable energy potential, with an estimated of 3.6 GW from bioenergy resources, comprising biomass (2.3 GW), biogas (736 MW), and municipal solid waste (MSW) (516 MW) (SEDA, 2021). The country's rapid population growth and urbanisation have further accelerated MSW generation, averaging 13.9 Mt annually (Ministry of Economy, 2023). At present, landfilling remains the dominant MSW management practice in Malaysia. In 2016, more than 80% of MSW was disposed in landfills and open dumps, resulting in 6,898,167 t CO₂-eq of greenhouse gas emissions. This is projected to rise to 9,991,486 t CO₂-eq by 2030 (Devados et al., 2021). On top of that, Malaysia's energy demand is projected to grow by 2% annually, driven by urbanisation and economic growth as well (IRENA, 2023). With this, the continued reliance on fossil-based energy would further hinder the nation's net-zero emissions target for 2050. In this context, converting MSW into electricity through waste-to-energy

(WtE) technologies has gained increasing attention as a solution to mitigate potential emissions from landfills and to reduce the reliance on fossil-based energy sources.

To support Malaysia's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) 2030 target – achieving 45% reduction in carbon intensity against GDP, Green Technology Financing Scheme (GTFS) has been introduced to stimulate the development and expansion of green technologies. Between 2010 and December 2020, this initiative contributed to an estimated reduction of 5.1 Mt CO₂-eq per year (MGTC, 2024). Building on this, the Malaysia Renewable Energy Roadmap identifies further action beyond 2025 is to improve and review the energy purchase framework for WtE projects. This is to ensure the cost of supporting such projects is equitably shared among electricity consumers (equitable socialisation cost). Nonetheless, several challenges remain:

- **Variation of tipping fee across Malaysia:** Tipping fee is a cost imposed for disposing waste at a landfill or WtE facility. In Malaysia, there is no fixed rate for tipping fee. Instead, it varies by region or state as these are typically determined by local authorities under broader waste management regulations – Solid Waste and Public Cleansing Management Act 2007 (AGC, 2017). This then complicates investment decisions as revenue streams differ depending on location.
- **Feedstock availability:** The recently launched Circular Economy Blueprint for Solid Waste in Malaysia promotes broad adoption of circular economy practice to minimise landfill disposal. This will gradually affect both the quantity and composition of feedstock available for WtE plants. According to KPKT (2025), the targeted amount of waste diverted from landfill is 9.04 million t per year by 2035, representing a 97% increase from the 2022 baseline.
- **Logistics and transportation cost:** Logistical challenges in waste collection and transport can affect the feedstock consistency. This in turn impacts plant capacity utilisation and revenue stability. To address this, the current tendering framework in Malaysia prioritises WtE projects located near to landfill sites with waste volumes exceeding 500 t per day (SEDA, 2021). While this approach mitigates the logistic cost issue, it creates a heavy dependence on large sites, excluding landfill with smaller scale and ultimately reducing the resilience of WtE development in the country.

1.1 Key economic factors

Currently, the Feed-in Tariff (FiT) rates for municipal solid waste-based projects in Malaysia range between RM 0.2687 per kWh to RM 0.3085 per kWh for plant capacity between 10 MW and 30 MW. While these tariffs provide a baseline for revenue estimation, they do not reflect the specific cost structure of a WtE projects. Additionally, WtE projects do capture additional revenue streams. Such includes the tipping fees from municipalities for waste disposal as well as the potential of carbon credit revenues from

emissions reduction. In Malaysia, tipping fee vary significantly, with reported value of RM 55 per t for Selangor state and RM 77 per t at the Bukit Payong WtE facility (The Edge Malaysia, 2023). This highlights the importance of evaluating how tipping fees affect financial viability and serve as a guideline to strategically developing an appropriate pricing mechanism. Moreover, ongoing efforts to strengthen waste circularity are expected to reduce the volume of feedstock available for WtE plant and further influencing their financial performance. For WtE projects with limited access to feedstock, additional transportation costs must also be considered to ensure stable feedstock supply and operation.

Therefore, a comprehensive financial analysis is needed to identify whether the current FiT rates are sufficient to ensure project bankability. Accordingly, this study examines the following research questions:

1. What is the threshold tipping fee required, and how does its variation affect the financial viability?
2. How does the feedstock availability influence the financial performance?
3. What is the financial trade-off between ensuring consistent feedstock supply and incurring higher logistic cost?

2. Methodology

This present work applies FINPLAN to study the financial viability of a 50 MW WtE plant located on the east coast of Malaysia, which has an estimated daily waste generation of 3,862 t (JPSPN, 2013). The financial performance is evaluated over the period 2026 to 2060, based on a financing structure of 20% equity and 80% debt, with 15% return on equity and discount rate of 6%. Key financial indicators including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Debt service coverage ratio (DSCR) and more, are calculated while incorporating the project's technical, economic, and financial parameters. The data used are extracted from journal articles, government publication, and national policy documents. **Table 1** summarises key technical parameters for the project.

Table 1. Technical parameters for the WtE project in Malaysia.

Item	Value	Unit	Basis of assumptions
Construction period	3	years	(Asim et al., 2023)
Plant life	25	years	
Electricity production	279.2	GWh/year	
Plant cost	151.0	M USD	
O&M	46.4	M MYR	10% of plant cost
Electricity cost (FiT rate)	0.2687	MYR/kWh	(SEDA, 2025)

The economic assumptions are as follows:

- Inflation rates are set at 3% and 4% for USD and MYR, respectively.
- The exchange rate is assumed at 4.9 MYR per USD; consistent with the relative inflation rates of 3%.

Whereas the financial assumptions are as follows:

- Financing includes Malaysia’s GTFS, with a 15-year tenor and 6% interest rate, capped at 15% of the total investment
- An interest rebate of 1.5% under GTFS is also considered to develop scenario analysis.
- Blended financing is proposed, comprising 65% export credit over 12 years at an interest rate of 3.5%.
- A commercial loan with 12-year tenor and an interest rate of 3% above inflation is considered.

3. Results

Table 2 summarised the five scenarios considered along with its corresponding NPV and IRR. The results demonstrate that the financing structure significantly influences project viability. For instance, the sole green financing through GTFS (scenario 2), even with rebate (scenario 3), is insufficient to yield positive returns due to its limited coverage (capped at 100 M MYR) and relatively higher interest (4.5 to 6%) compared to export credit options (3.5%). A positive NPVs can only be achieved starting from scenario 4, where blended financing that combines exiting GTFS and export credit is introduced. The performance further improved with the consideration of interest rebate (scenario 5). As the incorporation of export credit substantially improves financial performance, this highlights the importance of accessing low-interest and long-tenor financing instruments for WtE project.

Table 2. Financial performance of WtE under different financing schemes the respective NPV and IRR.

Scenarios	Assumptions	NPV, M MYR	IRR, %	
1	No financing scheme	Commercial loan	- 43.03	4.97
2	Green financing only	15% GTFS with 6% interest rate	- 42.68	4.93
3	Green financing with interest rebate	15% GTFS with 4.5% interest rate	- 36.09	5.13
4	Blended financing	65% export credit, 15% GTFS with 6% interest rate	18.17	6.38
5	Blended financing with interest rebate	65% export credit, 15% GTFS with 4.5% interest rate	23.89	6.50

The shift from negative to positive NPV between scenario 3 and 4 marks a critical financing threshold. Therefore, to fully capture the project's financial performance, scenario 4 is selected as the baseline for subsequent sensitivity analysis.

3.1 Sensitivity analysis 1: Tipping fee variation

The inclusion of tipping fees serves as an additional revenue stream for WtE projects, helping to improve financial viability and reduce dependence on the electricity sales alone. The first sensitivity analysis evaluates the impact of tipping fee variation on the financial viability of the WtE project. This analysis is benchmarked against two financial indicators: i. Debt service coverage ratio (DSCR) with a threshold of greater than 1.3 (generate 30% more income than the required debt payments), ii. Breakeven point ratio of less than 1 to ensure operational sustainability. Results shown in **Figure 1** reveal that the project requires a tipping fee within the range of 74.9 to 82.5 MYR per t to meet these thresholds. While this offers flexibility and opportunity for negotiation, the relatively narrow tipping fee band highlight that the financial viability of the project is highly sensitive to waste disposal revenue.

Figure 1. Sensitivity analysis of tipping fee variation to achieve DSCR > 1.5 and breakeven point ratio < 1.

3.2 Sensitivity analysis 2: Feedstock variation

Given the policy push under the Circular Economy Blueprint, future waste diversion could reduce the volume of waste available to maintain stable WtE operation. This ultimately affecting the stable operation of WtE plants as it leads to lower electricity production relative to the installed capacity. To enhance the project resilience under these conditions, carbon credit is incorporated as an additional revenue stream, reflecting the avoided emissions from landfills and the displacement of conventional fossil-based energy. As shown in **Figure 2**, the analysis indicates that the minimum feedstock threshold required to maintain financially feasible is 2,000 t per day for the case without

carbon credit and 1,700 t per day with carbon credit inclusion. This demonstrates that carbon credits can effectively reduce the project's reliance on high feedstock volumes while supporting its financial viability.

Figure 2. Sensitivity analysis of feedstock availability on the NPV and IRR under scenarios without and with carbon credit inclusion.

3.3 Sensitivity analysis 3: Additional transportation cost

This analysis evaluates the additional logistic expenses of supplying feedstock from a range of distance required to maintain a stable supply to the WtE plant. The varying distance considered are as listed follow – baseline (near to large landfill sites), short distance (<5 km), moderate distance (5 to 10 km), long distance (10 to 20 km), and remote (> 20km). The results shown in **Figure 3** indicate that the project remains financially viable only when transportation distance is below 5 km, at which beyond this threshold the NPVs turn negative. This also reveal that feedstock supply stability is not only a volume issue but also a logistic cost concern.

Figure 3. Sensitivity analysis of MSW transportation distance on the NPV and IRR.

4. Discussion

The analysis highlights the importance of blended financing frameworks that integrate existing domestic green financing scheme into WtE project. While GTFS serve as a useful enabler, its limited coverage reduces its effectiveness in supporting capital-intensive infrastructure. Sensitivity analysis on tipping fee variation further indicates the financial viability is highly sensitive to waste disposal revenue, which requires a minimum of 74.9 MYR/t to ensure financial resilience (DSCR > 1.3) and breakeven point of < 1. Therefore, region with lower tipping fee may render projects unbackable. Additionally, WtE projects require a consistent waste supply, making it vulnerable to the implementation of circular economy policies and increasing recycling targets. While both waste diversion and energy recovery are important, this highlights the need for policies that ensure sufficient feedstock allocation for WtE plants while supporting broader recycling and sustainability goals. External revenue such as carbon credit could help mitigate these risks. Finally, logistics remain a key operational constraint. The continued reliance on large nearby landfills reduces flexibility and resilience, while sourcing from small or distance sites increases cost. Based on these findings, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- **Facilitate access to Climate Finance Channels:** To support financing frameworks that combine GTFS with other affordable funding options, it is essential to assist WtE developers in accessing domestic and international climate finance instruments, in alignment with Malaysia’s climate finance landscape.
- **Tipping Fee Pricing Mechanisms:** Establish a standardised and consistent tipping fee framework to reduce risk for investors. Additionally, this ensure financial viability for developers while remaining affordable for municipalities. In

addition, the government can provide guarantees (e.g., minimum tipping fee guarantees) to ensure project earns minimum guaranteed income.

- **Carbon Incentives:** Incorporation of appropriately priced carbon credit mechanism to provide additional revenue. This could lower feedstock availability threshold and improve resilience against policy-drive waste diversion.
- **Logistics and Plant Planning:** Strategic landfill planning is essential to optimise feedstock logistics and reduce operational risk.

This study does not account for certain policy and market dynamics, such as potential changes in waste management regulation or fluctuation in the carbon credit market. In addition, other potential revenue streams (i.e., by-product, heat) were not considered. These areas present opportunities for future research to further enhance the financial assessment of WtE projects.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated the financial viability of a 50 MW WtE project in Malaysia using FINPLAN, considering technical, economic, and financial parameters. Scenario analysis showed that positive project viability is only achieved under blended financing schemes, highlighting the limitations of GTFS alone in supporting capital-intensive infrastructure. Sensitivity analyses further revealed that WtE projects are highly dependent on tipping fees, consistent feedstock availability, and logistics, while complementary revenue streams, such as carbon credits, can improve resilience and lower the minimum feedstock threshold. Based on these findings, several policy recommendations are proposed. Furthermore, future research should explore dynamics financial conditions and policy changes to provide a more comprehensive assessment of WtE project feasibility in Malaysia.

References

AGC, 2017. *Solid Waste and Public Cleansing Management Act 2007*. Attorney General's Chambers of Malaysia.

Asim, M., Kumar, R., Kanwal, A., Shahzad, A., Ahmad, A. & Farooq, M., 2023. Techno-economic assessment of energy and environmental impact of waste-to-energy electricity generation. *Energy Reports*, 10, pp.3373-3382.

Devados, M.P.S, Agamuthu, P., Mehran, S.B., Santha, C. & Fauziah, S.H., 2021. Implications of municipal solid waste management on greenhouse gas emissions in Malaysia and the way forward. *Waste Management*, 119, 135-144.

IRENA, 2023. *Malaysia Energy Transition Outlook*. International Renewable Energy Agency. Available at: https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2023/Mar/IRENA_Malaysia_energy_transition_outlook_2023.pdf [Accessed 3 September 2025].

JPSPN, 2013. *Survey on Solid Waste Composition, Characteristics & Existing Practice of Solid Waste Recycling in Malaysia*. National Solid Waste Management Department. Available at: https://jpspn.kpkt.gov.my/jpspn/resources/Images%20JPSPN/Sumber%20Rujukan/Kajian/Final_Report_REVz.pdf [Accessed 10 September 2025].

KPKT, 2025. *Circular Economy Blueprint for Solid Waste in Malaysia*. Ministry of Housing and Local Government. Available at https://www.kpkt.gov.my/kpkt/resources/user_1/GALERI/PDF_PENERBITAN/BUEPRINT/BUEPRINT_EKONOMI_KITARAN_SISA_PEPEJAL_DI_MALAYSIA_2025-2035-BI.pdf [Accessed 10 September 2025].

Ministry of Economy, 2023. *National Energy Transition Roadmap*. Ministry of Economy. Available at: <https://ekonomi.gov.my/sites/default/files/2023-08/National%20Energy%20Transition%20Roadmap.pdf> [Accessed 5 September 2025].

MGTC, 2024. *Green Technology Financial Scheme 4.0*. Malaysian Green Technology and Climate Change Corporation. Available at: <https://heyzine.com/flip-book/0bb4d1b600.html> [Accessed 10 September 2025].

SEDA, 2021. *Malaysia Renewable Energy Roadmap*. Sustainable Energy Development Authority (SEDA) Malaysia. Available at: https://www.seda.gov.my/reportal/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/MyRER_webVer3.pdf [Accessed 2 September 2025].

SEDA, 2025. *Feed-In Tariff (FiT) Rates*. Sustainable Energy Development Authority (SEDA) Malaysia. Available at: <https://www3.seda.gov.my/iframe/> [Accessed 2 September 2025].

The Edge Malaysia, 2023. PKNS-owned Worldwide builds up WTE assets, adds Bukit Payong project to portfolio. *The Edge Malaysia*. Available at: <https://theedgemalaysia.com/node/691691> [Accessed 9 September 2025].

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